

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Pilot Implementation

HerStory map excursion guidelines for à Fort-de-France (France)

WP2 D2.2

HerStory Consortium

Amendment History

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2	0	10/05/2024	Katarzyna Sopolinska	1st version of the guidelines for the excursion in Martinique
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3	0	15/05/2024	Katarzyna Sopolinska	2 nd version of the guidelines for the excursion in Martinique

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1. Introduction

The current document is developed to provide guidelines on tour excursion development, for monuments of women in local history and to ensure that the experience is educational, engaging, and respectful, a set of best approaches is presented below, to select the most suitable for each country.

The first phase of excursion will take place at a pilot phase with 160 persons in total (at least in the pilot excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total (**10**) **must be young people**. Following to the excursion, all partners will collect the feedback, make the necessary changes, and then prepare another excursión, the final one.

Final excursion will involve 160 persons in total (at least in the excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and least half of the total (**10**) **must be young people**. At the end a total of 320 participants (as a minimum), at least half of the total (160) must be young people.

The participants of the excursions will consist of young people and educators, trainers and academics:

- young people, boys, and girls,
- young people active in local community groups such as Municipalities' Youth Councils,
- students from the fields of History,
- students from the fields of Gender Studies,
- youth experts,
- youth organizations,
- academics from the fields of History and Gender Studies,
- teachers and educators,
- teachers, and women and human rights organizations experts/activists.

Each partner will create different and specific activities for the excursions organized in their city, for the pilots and the final ones. A set of general guidelines are presented below and each partner will analyse and formulate the topics of the guidelines with additions in the excursion descriptions, based on each country specifics.

The target audience for the tour guide guidelines is:

- A. touristic offices and educators.
- B. Small groups (independent excursions)

This document outlines D'Antilles & D'Ailleurs' plan to organize a gamified tour around Fort de France in the form of a treasure hunt, in which groups will have the opportunity to explore the history of prominent women in the city. At different locations of the tour various questions are available to promote knowledge and curiosity within the group. For best results the group size should be around 20 people maximum.

2. Guidelines to develop a physical excursion

LEVEL 1: How to create a unique tour.

1. Define Objectives:

General objective:

Employing an interactive educational approach to highlight the contributions of Martinican women in the history of the island.

Specific objectives:

- Increase public awareness and understanding of the significant roles played by Martinican women in shaping the island's history, culture, and society.
- Recognize and celebrate the achievements, struggles, and resilience of Martinican women throughout history.
- Enhance the representation and visibility of Martinican women in historical narratives and public discourse, ensuring their stories are acknowledged and valued.
- Empower Martinican women by highlighting their agency, leadership, and impact, fostering a sense of pride and identity within the community.
- Encourage dialogue, reflection, and engagement among participants of the tour, promoting discussions on gender equality, social justice, and the ongoing struggle for women's rights.
- Promote feminist values of equality, inclusivity, and solidarity, emphasizing the importance of action and advocacy for gender justice.

- Highlight the work of local feminist associations in Fort-de-France, raising awareness about their initiatives, services, and support systems aimed at empowering women and addressing gender-based challenges.

2. Define the thematic of the excursion:

The tour highlights the social activism of women in Fort-de-France during the 19th and 20th centuries.

3. Recommend a rich educational content for each woman presented:

With extensive research and collaboration with local feminist organizations, we have collected historically accurate information about each woman and location. You can find all this information in the information sheet below.

LOCATION NUMBER	1
LOCATION	Le Carénage
WOMAN	Les charbonnières
INFORMATION	<p>The Carénage Center of Fort de France is located in the city's port, at Quai des Tourelles. Here, boats are maintained and repaired; it is also a storage area and a refueling station. Although the Carénage is now well-known as a departure point for ferries to the Caribbean islands with the "Express des Iles", in the past, it used to be the workplace of charcoal workers also called "Les Charbonnières".</p> <p>"Les Charbonnières" are women who in the 19th and 20th century played an important role in the social and working-class history of Martinique. Their job was to carry 40-kilo baskets on their heads to supply coal to the bunkers of the Compagnie Générale Transatlantique steamships that made the transatlantic crossing to export rum and sugar. It was a difficult, arduous and poorly-paid job. They were the first to organize themselves as a trade union and mutual aid and solidarity fund, and thus had a strong impact on the world of labor and trade unions.</p>

LOCATION NUMBER	2
LOCATION	Place Paulette Nardal
WOMAN	Paulette Nardal
INFORMATION	<p>This square was named after Paulette Nardal in the 1980s by Aimé Césaire, who was the mayor of Fort-de-France at the time.</p> <p>Born on October 12, 1896, in Le François, Paulette Nardal went to mainland France at the age of 24 to further her studies.</p> <p>In 1920, Paulette arrived in Paris to study English at the Sorbonne University. Paulette and her sister Jeanne, who studied literature, were the first Black female students at La Sorbonne.</p> <p>Every Sunday, Paulette and her sisters Jeanne and Andrée hosted a literary salon in their apartment, where they discussed the issue of women's emancipation and the black question. Césaire, Senghor, Damas and a host of other prominent figures would attend, enabling them to lay the groundwork for the theory of Négritude, a cultural, political and literary movement that emerged in Paris in the 1930s.</p> <p>In 1931, along with Haitian writer Léo Sajous and Guyanese writer René Maran, Paulette and Jeanne co-founded La Revue du Monde Noir, a bilingual French-English journal that served as a platform for black intellectuals and inspired intersectional feminism.</p> <p>Paulette returned to Martinique after the start of World War II, and following the ordinance of April 21, 1944, she founded the Rassemblement Féminin, the Martinican branch of the Union féminine civique et sociale, an association aimed at promoting the exercise of civil rights.</p> <p>The Nardal sisters, and Paulette and Jeanne in particular, were key figures in the intellectual and cultural Négritude movement in Martinique and France. They played a key role in the recognition and valorization of black culture and identity, and in the fight against racism and social injustice. But like many women, their ideas and contributions have been overshadowed or attributed to men.</p>

	<p>Paulette Nardal was awarded the Officer of the Académie des Palmes and Knight of the Legion of Honor. In the 1980s, Aimé Césaire had Paulette Nardal's name placed on a square in the city of Fort-de-France, where he served as mayor. In 2021, the city of Ducos renamed its high school in her honor. In 2018, the City of Paris decided to create the Jane-and-Paulette Nardal promenade in the 14th arrondissement, which was officially inaugurated by Anne Hidalgo in August 2019.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER	3
LOCATION	UFM, Espace Jane Léro
WOMAN	Jane Léro
INFORMATION	<p>The Union des Femmes de Martinique, founded in 1944, is a feminist association with the main mission of defending and promoting women's rights, thus contributing to the construction of a society of equality between women and men. This mission is structured around three main areas of intervention:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Welcoming and supporting women in difficulty or victims of violence. 2. Training and prevention, particularly on topics related to gender equality, combating discrimination, and violence against women. 3. Activism for women's emancipation, combating violence and sexist discrimination. <p>The Espace Jane Léro, the administrative headquarters of the association, houses various activity hubs, including the Training-Prevention hub, the Awareness-Raising hub, the Administrative and Financial hub, as well as the Angela Davis Resource Center.</p> <p>The place is named after Jane Léro, a Martinican activist and feminist renowned for her advocacy for women's rights and the promotion of gender equality in Martinique. She was the one who mobilized a and led a group of women for the establishment of the UFM, Union des Femmes de la Martinique, thus marking the inception of the first feminist organization in Martinique.</p>

	<p>Jane Léro (1916 – 1961) was a Martinican activist and feminist. She is known for her advocacy for women's rights and the promotion of gender equality in Martinique.</p> <p>In 1938, she received the honor prize in mathematics and sciences from the Schoelcher High School. She then wished to pursue higher studies in France, but only her two brothers were allowed to do so. This differential treatment sparked her first commitment to gender equality.</p> <p>A whole new field of conquests in the fight for women's rights opens up with the April 1944 ordinance that establishes the right to vote for women in French territory. On June 11, 1944, leading a group of women with communist leanings, Jane Léro mobilized for the creation of the UFM, l'Union des Femmes de la Martinique, the first feminist organization in Martinique.</p> <p>Her first objective will be to encourage women to exercise their right to vote. The second is to provide them with the means to raise their children, who are subject to malnutrition and illiteracy.</p> <p>Jane Léro is a significant figure in the social and political movements in Martinique during the 1940s and 1950s. She participated in local feminist movements and was a vocal advocate against gender inequalities and social injustices. She played an important role in raising awareness about the specific issues faced by Martinican women at that time and her work contributed to paving the way for future advancements in the fight for gender equality in the society.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER	4
LOCATION	Rue du Commerce, formerly the headquarters of the 'Émancipation féminine' lodge.
WOMAN	Claude Carbet
INFORMATION	Claude Carbet (1893-1968), formerly known as Olympe Tricot, was a member of the "Émancipation féminine" lodge, marking the early stages of feminism in Martinique. Her 27-year relationship with Marie-Magdeleine Carbet (1902-1996), originally named Louise Eugénie Anna Marie-

	<p>Magdeleine, stirred controversy. Both women adopted the surname Carbet as a symbol of their Martinican heritage.</p> <p>On March 1, 1931, Claude Carbet delivered a public lecture titled "Female Emancipation and Human Rights," wherein she opposed all forms of inequality. She advocated for the rights of homosexuals, championed women's autonomy over their bodies, and campaigned for women's suffrage.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER	5
LOCATION	La Maison de Solange (UFM)
WOMAN	Solange Fitte-Duval
INFORMATION	<p>"La Maison de Solange" is a space of the Union des Femmes de la Martinique (UFM), welcoming women over 18 in distress and victims of violence. It was inaugurated on October 24, 2014 and bears the name of Solange Fitte-Duval (1921-2014), president of the UFM from 1973 to 1993, who led numerous actions for the promotion and emancipation of Martinican women and is considered a pioneer of feminism in Martinique.</p> <p>The House of Solange aims to be a space for support, respite, and exchange. The House of Solange comprises two facilities to address the distress of women victims of violence: the Listening, Information, and Support Space (EEIA) and the Day Reception (ADJ). UFM's social workers, trained and qualified, offer individual interviews, collective activities led by external speakers, thematic workshops, lawyer consultations, various services (luggage storage, computer access, dining area, restrooms, children's corner, library...).</p> <p>Detailed information about Solange Fitte Duval:</p> <p>Solange Fitte Duval was born on August 25, 1921, in Fort-de-France. She became a teacher in Sainte-Esprit and was actively involved in community life. Among her achievements, she was the founder of several organizations, including the "La Culture" association in Saint-Esprit, and the Martinican Center for Cultural Animation (CMAC). As a friend of Jane Léro, she played an active role in the creation of the UFM and opened its local branch in Saint-Esprit. She also spearheaded the birth of the feminist journal "Femmes</p>

	<p>martiniquaises." In 1973, she became the president of the UFM, a position she held for 20 years until 1993. Under her leadership, the association fought for the establishment of daycare centers, enabling women to pursue professional careers while raising children. She also provided night classes for women working in the sugarcane fields, many of whom were illiterate at the time. A primary school in Fort-de-France, in the Tivoli neighborhood, bears her name.</p>
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4. Define a compelling excursion tour content:

Additional visual materials will be shared with the participants of the tour.

Une charbonnière <https://familyevasion.com/les-charbonnieres-une-histoire-de-droits>

A Fort-de-France, ce sont les femmes qui chargent le charbon sur les grands navires de la Compagnie Générale Transatlantique.

<https://www.martinique.franceantilles.fr/actualite/societe/memoire-sensible/une-vie-de-charbonniere-827655.php>

Jeanne Léro militante communiste issue de la classe moyenne. • ©Martinique la 1ère
<https://la1ere.francetvinfo.fr/martinique/8-mars-histoire-lutte-feministe-martinique-808223.html>

Paulette Nardal. France Info, Outre-mer la 1^{ère}. Publié le 10/03/2020

<https://la1ere.francetvinfo.fr/paulette-nardal-l-architecte-oubliee-de-la-negritude-1307348.html>

Claude Carbet franc-maçonne membre de la loge « Émancipation féminine ». ©Martinique la 1^{ère}

<https://la1ere.francetvinfo.fr/martinique/8-mars-histoire-lutte-feministe-martinique-808223.html>

Solange Fitte-Duval, AZMartinique

<https://azmartinique.com/fr/tout-savoir/personnages-celebres/solange-fitte-duval>

5. Tour Excursion Planning:

The tour is scheduled to last 90 minutes, including all discussions. We've selected Tropiques Atrium, a national stage located centrally, as the meeting point for its easy recognition and proximity to the first tour location – Le Carénage.

After the final stop at La Maison de Solange, participants will head to our association's garden, just a 3-minute walk away, to share tour feedback in a tranquil setting over refreshments.

The tour itinerary is as follows:

Meeting point: In front of the Tropiques Atrium building

1. Le Carénage
2. Place Paulette Nardal
3. UFM (Espace Jane Léro)
4. Loge d'Émancipation Féminine
5. La Maison de Solange (UFM)

Ending point: The garden of Le Trois Lieu (122 rue Lamartine)

LEVEL 2: How to implement an exciting tour.

1. Add Interactive Elements to excursion tour:

If the HerStory mobile app is developed before the pilot, we will utilize it to enhance the interactivity of the tour. Additionally, we have prepared a series of questions to prompt active participation. Finally, to gather feedback from the participants after the tour experience, DADA will host a closing discussion in its garden situated in the heart of Fort-de-France.

List of questions prepared :

LOCATION	WOMAN	QUESTION(S)
Le Carénage	Les charbonnières	<p>1. What was the work of the charcoal burners (“les charbonnières”)?</p> <p>A) Prepare coal for sale and distribution</p> <p>B) Supply coal to factory furnaces</p> <p>C) Mine coal in the mines</p> <p>D) Supply coal to steamships</p> <p>2. How many kilograms did the baskets that the charcoal burners put on their heads to transport coal weigh?</p> <p>A) 5 kg</p>

		<p>B) 10 kg</p> <p>C) 40 kg</p> <p>D) 60 kg</p>
Place Paulette Nardal	Paulette Nardal	<p>1. What was Paulette Nardal's field of study at La Sorbonne?</p> <p>A) Mathematics</p> <p>B) Literature</p> <p>C) History</p> <p>D) English</p> <p>2. Which literary movement was influenced by Paulette Nardal?</p> <p>A) Symbolism</p> <p>B) Dadaism</p> <p>C) Negritude</p> <p>D) Impressionism</p>
UFM, Espace Jane Léro	Jane Léro	<p>1. When did Jane Léro found the Union des Femmes de Martinique?</p> <p>A) in June 1920</p> <p>B) in June 1944</p> <p>C) in June 1945</p> <p>D) in June 1968</p>

		<p>2. When did women in France first gain the right to vote in elections?</p> <p>A) February 21, 1848</p> <p>B) March 15, 1944</p> <p>C) April 21, 1944</p> <p>D) August 28, 1962</p>
<p>Loge « Émancipation féminine »</p>	<p>Claude Carbet</p>	<p>1. What is Claude Carbet's birth name?</p> <p>A) Claudia Tricot</p> <p>B) Marie-Magdeleine Tricot</p> <p>C) Olympe Tricot</p> <p>D) Daphné Tricot</p> <p>2. Which themes did Claude Carbet often explore in her writings?</p> <p>A) Romance and adventure</p> <p>B) Political satire</p> <p>C) Colonial oppression and women's rights</p> <p>D) Scientific exploration</p>

<p>La Maison de Solange (UFM)</p>	<p>Solange Fitte-Duval</p>	<p>1. How long did Solange Fitte Duval serve as president of the UFM?</p> <p>A) 10 years</p> <p>B) 15 years</p> <p>C) 20 years</p> <p>D) 25 years</p> <p>2. Who is the target audience of La Maison de Solange?</p> <p>A) Illiterate women</p> <p>B) Women victims of violence</p> <p>C) Undocumented women</p> <p>D) Homeless women</p>
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C. Verify accessibility and provide necessary information:

All locations are accessible to people with reduced mobility.

D. Receive Feedback and Improvement:

At the end of the pilot excursion, the participants will be invited to enjoy a refreshing drink in DADA's garden, located in the city center of Fort-de-France, near the final tour location. This will be an opportunity to discuss their satisfaction with the tour and fill out the evaluation questionnaires. First, participants will be asked to complete the HerStory evaluation, which will help us make any necessary improvements to enhance future tour experiences. Then, we will also share with them the European Commission survey to complete.

E. Engage Locals through Collaborations:

Experts have been involved in identifying locations related to women, and they have provided their expertise to ensure that the information we collected is historically accurate. Our main collaboration has been with the association Culture Égalité, a feminist organization based in Fort-de-France. Among other potential partners, we have identified the association UFM (Union des Femmes de la Martinique).

LEVEL 3: Generic guidelines for individual and self-guided tours.

1. Enable the customization of excursions:

The pilot tours within the HerStory project are scheduled to take place between April and June 2024. At the end of June, our association will host an artist residency aimed at training young people in using artist techniques (a combination of activism and art) to promote gender equality. Participants in this training could be a suitable target group for our pilot excursions, as their involvement could enhance their understanding of the contributions of Martinican women to gender equality.

Regarding the final tours of the project, they can be organized around the following key dates: September 18 (International Equal Pay Day) or October 11 (International Day of the Girl Child).

2. Develop options for Training Guides or/and self-guided tours:

We highly recommend designing the tour as a treasure hunt adventure. In this case, during the tour, the guide will pose questions to the participants, and correct answers will unlock clues leading to the next tour location. These clues could be in the form of images or different types of hints, guiding participants to decode their next destination.

A treasure hunt offers several advantages. Treasure hunts are engaging activities and require participants to be active and involved especially if questions are asked during the tour. This can improve the learning experience and retention of information, while making the experience more memorable.

Alternatively, the tour can also be organized as a self-guided tour. In a self-guided tour, participants explore a destination or attraction at their own pace, without the need for a traditional tour guide. Instead of following a guide, participants typically use a map, guidebook, audio guide, or mobile app to navigate the tour route and learn about points of interest along the way.

Self-guided tours offer flexibility and independence, allowing participants to choose their own starting point, pace, and schedule. They are often designed to be completed individually or in small groups, giving participants the freedom to explore at their leisure.

For the organization of a self-guided tour, the HerStory mobile app, as well as the HerStory online platform and map, will be very useful resources. We recommend checking and, if

needed, adapting the itinerary of the tour beforehand. Additionally, thorough research on the places and women identified beforehand is essential for fully enjoying the tour and gaining a deeper understanding of the historical significance of each location.

Extra tips.

Having a QRCode printed to go to the local map of the city, so people can follow the tour or access to the guidelines to make the tour in an educational way.

2. Documentation and templates

The deliverables of WP4 activities are presented below:

D4.1 HERSTORY MAP pilot implementation

- **Invitation/ agenda/ program:** A template will be shared by KEAN.
- **Signed attendance list**
- **Minutes/ report (tbd)**
- **Other evidence** (in case of pictures we need consent forms)